

The Production of Metal Matrix Composites by Die Casting Processes and its Mechanical Properties

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Abstract

The die casting process is considered as an attractive way to form the primary product of near net shape metal matrix composites [MMCs] for wide use in automobile and aerospace industries.

To understand the possibility of MMCs fabrication by die casting processes, which molten metal have been infiltrated into the fiber preforms, and the fiber preforms of volume fraction 15% and 25% were fabricated by vacuum pumping and speed control press. The optimal condition for preform fabrication by using water, the inorganic binder and measured Saffil alumina short fiber amount have been experimentally obtained. A controlled amount of molten metal was poured into the preheated die with preheated preform, and then the die pressure was applied until complete solidification is achieved. Therefore, the short fiber reinforced MMCs was fabricated by forced infiltration of molten metals into fiber preform under an appropriate casting speed.

The dispersion states of the fibers were observed. The preform deformation behaviors of fabricated composites are discussed. The breakage of the fibers, deformation of fiber preform and tensile fracture surface are also observed for composites, and the mechanical properties such as tensile strength, the modulus and hardness of MMCs are measured at the room temperature.

key words : Metal Matrix Composites, preform fabrication, Infiltration, die casting processes, Injection velocity.

1. Introduction

The high cost manufacturing of near net shape metal matrix composites [MMCs] with reinforcement is a major reason limiting their commercial application. In spite of their attractive properties, such as high specific strength and stiffness, high temperature performance and wear resistance, the MMCs had been used in aerospace industries for airframe and spacecraft structures.

More recently, the automotive, electronic, and leisure industries have been using these composites. In these applications, the low cost manufacturing technique for MMCs is a major concern. The several low cost manufacturing techniques for MMCs have recently been developed based on casting technologies, such as Squeeze casting⁽¹⁾⁻⁽⁶⁾, Compo casting⁽⁷⁾⁻⁽⁹⁾, Continuous casting⁽¹⁰⁾ and Stirring method⁽¹¹⁾⁻⁽¹²⁾. In the present paper, the Al₂O₃ SAFFIL fibers reinforced ADC10 aluminum alloy matrix composites have been fabricated by die casting processes. In die casting processing, a relatively high velocity compared to squeeze casting is rapidly applied on the molten metal to effect infiltration of the molten metal into the fiber preform in preheated die. To investigate the possibility of MMCs fabrication by die casting techniques, the fiber preforms were fabricated by vacuum

pumping and drain system. According to die casting processes, the manufacturing techniques of the economical MMCs are possible, and the various kinds of the application can be expected in a wide industrial field because of its high productivity and excellent near shape formability. As a result of this study, a processing for die casting of Al_2O_3 short fiber reinforced MMCs has been developed, and the mechanical properties of MMCs, such as tensile strength, hardness and modulus of elasticity are obtained, and SEM micrographs in tensile fracture surface are also observed.

2. Experimental

2.1 Manufacturing of fibre preforms.

The reinforcement materials used is SAFFIL Al_2O_3 short fiber with average diameter $3\mu m$, density $3.3\sim 3.5\text{ g/cm}^3$ and two kinds of the fiber length $70, 200\mu m$. The fiber is fabricated into preform to give a final machine part composed of given dimensions and volume fraction. Fig.1 (a)~(c) show the experimental procedure that was used for the purpose of preform fabrication. The main function of experimental apparatus has been explained as the following three main parts.

- (1) Measurement part ①⑤
- (2) Plastic mold for preform fabrication ②③
- (3) Drain system and vacuum pump for volume fraction control ⑥⑦

The two kinds of short fibers of the $200\mu m$ and $70\mu m$ for preforms fabrication are mixed homogeneously with water accompanied by small amounts of inorganic binder to avoid a preform deformation and disorder of fiber during die casting respectively, and to keep permanent shape in preform fabrication processing. The fabricated slurry fibers are poured into a plastic mold as shown in Fig.1, and drained by a vacuum pump within a given time, then pressing until an appropriate volume fraction is obtained. The main processing parameters of preform fabrication are an amount of binder, stirring time, stirring speed, settlement time of fibers, drain pressure, drain time and an amount of water. In order to obtain homogeneously dispersed fiber preforms and no macro-void in preform surface, preliminary experiments were performed to optimize the conditions of vacuum-pressure processes. The preform-fabrication conditions for above processing parameters are obtained by the method of trial and error, as shown in Table.1 .

Figure.1 (a)~(c) Fabrication processes of short fiber preform

Table.1 Preform fabrication conditions of volume fraction 15% and 25% for variation of fiber length

Fiber length, l_f [μm]	Preform size (t×w×l) [mm]	Amount of binder(V_b) [cc]	Amount of water(V_w) [cc]	Stirring time(t_s) [min]	Stirring speed(t_v) [rpm]	Settlement time(t_s) [min]	Drain pressure(P_a) [cmHg]	Drain time(t_d) [min]
200	24×24×130	15.6	880	15	110	50	20	20
70	14×24×130	15.6	550	15	110	35	15~18	50~55

In case of fiber length 200 μm , a very small pressure was applied to control the volume fraction $V_f = 15\%$ after a dewatering process was performed to keep the final preform shape, and another preform with fiber volume fraction 25% could be obtained without applied pressure for fiber length 70 μm . In this preform fabrication processes, the applied pressure was not measured because it was very small, and the punch pressuring velocity is 10 mm sec⁻¹. The two kinds of preforms were fabricated by above condition. The fabricated preform was dried in a dry oven of 150°C temperature.

3. Manufacturing of composites

A pressurized metal indirect die casting is a process by which a molten metal alloy is injected under high velocity into a cavity form between steel die. The main benefit of using the high pressure indirect die casting is the advantage of obtaining fine geometrix detail of a cast part as it solidifies within the precision machined mold cavity. The base alloy used for this study is an ADC10 casting aluminum alloy. Table.2 shows the standard composition of such alloys.

Table.2 Chemical composition used base materials of metal matrix composites

Cu	Si	Mg	Zn	Fe	Mn	Ni	Sn	Al
2.81	9.31	0.51	0.61	0.84	0.26	0.09	0.03	bal

A TOSHIBA die casting machine has been used throughout this work capable of 135 ton, a plunger diameter and stroke of these machine are 50 mm and 305 mm respectively. The injection velocities at the ranging from 0.1 to 3.6 m/sec were used to fabrication of Al₂O₃ short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites. The die construction and the schematic diagram of the apparatus used in indirect die casting processes for fabrication of MMCs are shown in Fig.2 (a)~(d). The preheated preform is set into the preheated die cavity of Fig. 2 (b), and a weight of molten metal is poured into the mold, as shown in Fig.2 (c). The dies are closed, and a pressure is applied until complete solidification during indirect die casting, as shown in Fig.2 (d). Finally, the metal matrix composites part is ejected after holding for 6 sec to improve the interface bonding between matrix and fiber. Most experiments were carried out at die temperatures of 180°C but some were carried out at lower temperatures, down to 160°C. The sleeve temperature was maintained at 180°C throughout the indirect die casting process. The three kinds of injection velocities ranging from 0.1 to 3.6 m/sec were used to experiment. In the die casting processes of molten metal, preform temperature of 680~700°C and molten metal temperatures of 670~700°C were applied. The test specimens were given a heat treatment at 170°C for 4 hours and quenched in water in order to eliminate residual stress.

Then, injection pressure was controlled more than 95 kg/cm² for low injection velocity.

Figure.2 (a)~(d) Indirect die casting processes for short fiber reinforced metal matrix composites fabrication

4. Experimental results

Fig.3 (a)~(c) show infiltration characteristics of metal matrix composites for preform thickness of 24mm for variation of injection velocity in die casting processes. It was clear that infiltration length of the composites increased with a decrease in ejection velocity, as shown in Fig.3 (a)~(c). The infiltration velocity of molten metal front generally relates to the infiltration pressure. However, both parameters cannot be controlled at the same time in die casting processes. According to the Darcy's law for non-uniform cross section of flow gaps, the faster the injection velocity, the higher required applied pressure. However, the forces applied to move the infiltration front are forces on a fluid element due to surface tension, viscosity, gravity and the end drag. The actual pressure used to infiltration is very small compared to the final die casting pressure.

Therefore, the optimum temperature control for various die casting process parameters and an appropriate injection velocity are required to complete infiltration. The die casting conditions are that of a lower velocity of 0.1 m/sec, die temperature of 160~180°C, molten metal temperature of 700°C and preform temperature of 680~700°C resulting in infiltrated Al₂O₃ short fiber/Al alloy composites, as shown in Fig.3 (c). Therefore, to infiltration of molten metal through the preform in spite of high injection velocity, the higher required preform temperature, in order to avoid solidification of the liquid on the surface of the preform, as shown in Fig.3 (a)~(b). It was found that the infiltration length depended mainly on the injection velocity.

Fig.4 (a)(b) show fiber preform deformation for the fabricated metal matrix composites by using 200 μm home-made preform and 50 μm commercial KAOWOOL preform respectively. The deformation value of the home-made preform is about 2mm larger than that of the fiber length of 50μm commercial KAOWOOL preform in central cross section parts of composites. In these experimental results, when the used fiber preform is less than the volume fraction of the 15%, it was difficult to infiltrated the molten metal without preform deformation. This is interpreted as a joint result of preform compression by the pressurized infiltrating metal and formation of solid metal between the fibers during infiltration, which prevents the relaxation of compresses preforms with infiltration stops⁽¹³⁾.

Figure.3 (a)~(c) Appearance of metal matrix composites showing infiltration characteristics for variation of injection velocity

- (a) $v = 0.1 \text{ m/sec}$
- (b) $v = 0.6 \text{ m/sec}$
- (c) $v = 3.6 \text{ m/sec}$

Figure.4 (a)(b) Preform deformation shape in metal matrix composites fabricated by indirect die casting

- (a) $70\mu\text{m}$ home made preform
- (b) $50\mu\text{m}$ KAOWOOL commercial preform

The effect of the preform and composites fabrication processes parameters on the preform deformation are mainly an amount of binder, injection velocity of a molten metal and the volume fraction.

Fig.5 shows the flexural tensile strength of the base alloy and the Al_2O_3 short fibers reinforced composites under the condition of Fig.3 (c). The average tensile strength of the fiber length of $200\mu\text{m}$ reinforced heat treated composites is 190.6 MPa larger than these of base alloy. In general, the tensile strength of the composites decreases with a decrease in fiber length. A probable reason is the lack of strenghtening due to the fibers length was shortened. The average tensile strength was 275.3 MPa for home made preform with the fiber length of $200\mu\text{m}$ [$200\mu\text{m}$ -Home] reinforced composites, 305.2 MPa for same preform reinforced heat treated composites [$200\mu\text{m}$ -Home-H.T]. The tensile strength of the fiber length $200\mu\text{m}$ reinforced heat treated 15 vol-% composites is larger than these of non-heat treated composites, as shown in Fig.3. The reason for this difference is due to thermal residual stresses. In case of the 25 vol-% composites, the effectiveness of heat treatment was not found. This may be indicative of non-optimum heat treatment conditions.

Fig.6 shows the modulus of elasticity for various fibers reinforced composites and base alloy. The average modulus of elasticity the $200\mu\text{m}$ -Home made preform reinforced heat treat composites ($200\mu\text{m}$ -Home-H.T) is 88.7 GPa , which is about two times as large as that of base alloy. The reinforcement content and fiber length are the dominant factor to determining the modulus of elasticity.

Fig.7 shows rockwell hardness R_B for various fibers reinforced composites and base alloy. The effect of increasing the volume fraction was to slightly increase the magnitude of hardness. However, for a fiber length of the 70 - $200\mu\text{m}$ home made preforms reinforced composites, there was no difference between the heat treated composites and not heat treated composites.

Fig.8 (a)~(c) show the fiber distribution in cross sections. The distribution of fibers was fairly uniform in all the composites.

Short fibers reinforced composites

200 μ m-HOME ; Composites with fiber length 200 μ m,
 200 μ m-HOME-H.T ; Heat treat composites with
 fiber length 200 μ m,

70 μ m-HOME ; Composites with fiber length 70 μ m,
 70 μ m-HOME-H.T ; Heat treat composites with
 fiber length 70 μ m,

ADC ; Casting Aluminum alloy
 50 μ m-KAOWOOL ; Composites with KAOWOOL Preform
 of fiber length 50 μ m

Figure.5 Tensile strength for a various fiber reinforced composites :

Short fibers reinforced composites

Figure.6 Modulus of elasticity for a various fiber reinforced composites

Fig.9 (a)~(c) show the tensile fractured surface for the three kinds of the fiber reinforced aluminum alloy composites. In SEM fractograph showing in Fig.9 (a)~(c), the tensile strength decreases with an increase of void size in the fracture surface and pulled out fibres. The void size and pulled out fibers were larger in short fiber length of the 200 μ m reinforced composites than in the fiber length of the 70 μ m reinforced composites, even if the infiltration has externally been very good as shown in Fig. 3(c).

In the case of the fiber length 50 μ m commercial KAOWOOL preform, infiltration is also very good but the wetting is not perfect and debonding also occurs as illustrated in Fig. 9 (c). The reason for this defect is that the more applied pressure and increasing of holding time to improve of the interface bonding between fiber and matrix are needed because the fiber surface area increases with a decrease in fiber length.

As a consequence, a holding time of more than 6 sec is suitable to ensure perfectly bonding between fiber and matrix alloy under lower injection velocity of about 0.6 m/sec to complete infiltration.

Short fibers reinforced composites

Figure.7 Rockwell hardness for a various fiber reinforced composites

Figure.8 (a)~(c) Optical micrographs from 15vol-%
200 μ m home made reinforced composites :
transverse section taken a height of approximately

(a) 3 mm (b) 10 mm (c) 18 mm

Figure.9 (a)~(c) SEM fractograph for a various
fiber length reinforced composites

(a) 200 μ m (b) 70 μ m (c) 50 μ m

Summary

1. The optimal condition for Al_2O_3 short fiber preform fabrication has been obtained by control of the processes parameters such as amount of binder and water, stirring time and speed, settlement time, drain time, and drain pressure.
2. Indirect die casting method has been applied to fabricate Al_2O_3 short reinforced aluminum matrix composites with the fiber volume fraction 15% and 25%.
It has been determined that the thickness preforms of 24mm are completely infiltrated by molten metal under condition of lower injection velocity of 0.6 m/sec, die temperature ranging from 160 to 200°C, preform temperature 700°C and molten metal temperature 680~700°C.
3. The void formation at the poor infiltrated of molten metal or pull out of fibers associated with debonding at the fiber-matrix interface are investigated due to poor holding time.

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